

GENERATING INNOVATIONS AND IMPROVEMENT OF PERFORMANCE OF COMPANIES USING KNOWLEDGE CHAIN MODEL

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Abstract

Modern business conditions, characterized by general uncertainty embodied in the permanent and intermittent changes, demand constant innovation from business entities. This is precisely why entrepreneurship and knowledge-based information are in constant focus of the scientific community. As an intangible resource, knowledge possesses unlimited possibilities of application as well as the status of the most valuable personal and organizational asset. It can be understood as encompassing of all that the company knows, the way it uses its knowledge and the speed at which it adopts something new and creates new knowledge. Its share in the increase of the company's value is growing, which should represent the point of special attention when the management of this resource is in question.

Knowledge management (KM) is a systematic process of organizational creation, storage, sharing and applying of knowledge. Its aim is to create individual knowledge, its transformation into collective knowledge and proper use of all forms of it in order to achieve further innovation and higher profitability of the company. On the one hand, this requires a formalization of tacit knowledge into explicit, and, on the other hand, the use of explicit knowledge to improve existing and create new implicit knowledge.

The efforts of knowledge management, time and investment it requires often face condemnation in the context of economic inefficiency. The reason lies in the inability to observe the connection between the activities of knowledge management and organizational performance. Porter's concept of its value chain offered a tool for identifying, analyzing and evaluating the contribution of each activity performed by the company in order to deliver its final value to the customer. The subject of our research is the application and adaptation of Porter's generic value chain in the process of knowledge management. The goal is to create a framework that will enable the identification and observation of the connection between knowledge management initiatives as well as a competitive advantage. The possibility of modeling the knowledge management activities in order to create a useful tool for their analysis and interpretation is being considered. Such an instrument is called the knowledge chain model and, same as Porter's value chain, includes nine generic activities that the company performs in managing their knowledge resources. The knowledge chain model is used as bases for the identification of the knowledge management activities, their contribution to the degree of influence upon the process of knowledge creation and determination of how valuable they are, how rare, difficult to imitate and sustainable over time. In this way we get an insight into the competitive position which can range from the competitive standstill, through equity and temporary competitiveness to sustainable competitive advantage which should be every company's goal.

Keywords: *knowledge chain model, knowledge resources, knowledge management, competitive advantage, value chain*

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Introduction

The success of a company in conditions of general uncertainty depends on uniqueness and the use of resources at its disposal, as well as on the frequency and intensity of the impact of external forces on the determinants of its operations. Resources are relatively fixed set of tangible and intangible assets controlled and exploited by a company in order to create value. The value creation process used to be primarily based on the transformation of physical capital (land, factories and equipment), physical (manual) labor and financial capital into outputs of greater value. However, possession of material assets that can be described as rare, valuable, unable to imitate and non-replaceable is getting harder to achieve in a dynamic, unpredictable and complex environment. This condition initiated the need for companies to focus on other types of resources, primarily non-material assets (Krstić and Vukadinović, 2008; Spinello, 1998).

Intangible assets are often described as intangible property because they have no "rigid" shape, as in case of buildings and equipment. They are also known by the term "hidden assets" because their financial value is not as obvious as in case of tangible assets and the same thing goes for their contribution to value creation (Kolaković, 2003). Worker's knowledge, patents, licenses, databases, know-how, systems of communication, coordination, controls, information systems and the like are often marked as constituent elements of intangible assets and they are all manifestations of explicit⁸⁸ and implicit⁸⁹ enterprise knowledge. As an intangible resource, knowledge possesses unlimited possibilities of application as well as the status of the most valuable personal and organizational asset. It can be understood as encompassing of all that a company knows, the way it uses its knowledge and the speed at which it adopts something new and creates new knowledge. Its share in the increase of the company's value is growing, which should represent the point of special attention when the management of this resource is in question.

Knowledge management is a systematic process of organizational creation, storage, sharing of knowledge and its application. It aims to create individual knowledge, transforms it into collective knowledge and ensures proper use of all its forms of in order to achieve further innovation and higher profitability of a company. This requires, on the one hand, a formalization of tacit knowledge into explicit, and, on the other hand, the use of explicit knowledge to improve existing and create new implicit knowledge.

In order to exploit the competitive potential of knowledge management it is necessary to possess an appropriate model or framework for identifying knowledge management activities that create value. Accordingly, application and adaptation of Porter's generic value chain on the knowledge management process designed so-called knowledge chain model.

The knowledge chain model

The knowledge chain model was developed by a group of experts in the field of knowledge management and based on the principles of Delphi method. As a starting point, they used Porter's generic value chain they illustrated as a set of activities focused on creating value for the customer (products/services) and generating value for owners (operating profit). Generic categories of the value chain were divided into two groups of activities: primary activities (which directly contribute to creating value for the customer and include: inbound logistics, operations, outbound logistics, marketing and sales, and service) and support activities (which contribute to the

⁸⁸ Knowledge that can be codified, documented and legally protected and materialized in the form of commercialized products, or equipment and procedures that the company uses in its business process.

⁸⁹ Knowledge that is informal, vaguely articulated and carried by an individual. Its presence is evident in the relationship among employees, organizational routines, organizational culture, etc.

effectiveness and efficiency of the primary activities and include: procurement, technology development (including R & D), human resource management, and infrastructure) (Porter, 1985). Grouping of value-making activities was based on the principle of their strategic and technological distinctiveness rather than their functional attributes.

Analogous to Porter's value chain, the knowledge chain model consists of five primary groups of activities that are performed in the process of knowledge resource management and four secondary groups of activities that support and guide the performance of primary activities (Figure 1).

Figure 1: *The knowledge chain model*
(Holsapple and Jones, 2004, p. 158; Holsapple and Jones, 2005, p. 5)

Displayed groups of activities are constitutive elements of the of knowledge management process. These activities are performed by processors (embodied in the form of people or machines) using resource knowledge and initiating costs whose level must be lower than the value of the process (Amaravadi and Lee, 2005). The results of the knowledge management process are manifested in the form of organizational learning (i.e., increasing levels of organizational knowledge) and projections (i.e., placing company's resources with the component of knowledge in the business environment). In addition to nine categories of activities, the results of the knowledge management process can be influenced by other resources controlled by the company as well as by the environment inside which it operates. The level of enterprise competitiveness depends on the degree by which it can increase its organizational knowledge and place it in the environment.

The primary activities of the knowledge chain model

The primary activities of the knowledge chain model are the stages in the knowledge management process. Although Figure 1 indicates the sequential nature of the links between these activities, they can be executed in a different order and even overlap, thanks to the specific features of knowledge resources. Depending on the type of enterprise and the knowledge management needs, each of the featured categories of primary activities can be divided into immediate, more distinctive activities. On the other hand, all categories of primary activities are, to a certain level, general which means that they can be identified inside all companies that implement knowledge management.

Primary activities include five generic categories (Holsapple and Jones, 2004):

1. **Knowledge acquisition** is a phase of the knowledge management process that begins with the identification of knowledge in the external environment and ends with his transformation into a form that the company can use in its operations. Direct acquisition refers to activities that are directly aimed at the acquisition of knowledge, such as obtaining/licensing data sets; obtaining/licensing patents, copyrights, using competitive intelligence, looking for windows of opportunity, obtaining trade secrets, soliciting knowledge from external sources; reviewing professional literature; monitoring technological advances; receiving external training; participating in collaborative acquisition. Unlike direct acquisition, indirect acquisitions are created by means of performing the companies' activities that are not primarily oriented toward achieving the knowledge acquisition targets, but still lead to it. This includes activities such as: hiring an employee, recruiting those with expertise, improving processes through purchase of technology, informally collecting comments from clients, using relationships for acquisition of information, etc. In general, all indirect acquisition activities can be divided into indirect acquiring knowledge en masse and indirect acquiring knowledge on an individual level.
2. **Knowledge selection** encompasses a set of activities aimed introvert, in contrast to externally oriented knowledge acquisition. These are the activities that serve as the basis for identification of knowledge within the existing resources of companies' knowledge and then provide its availability - in an appropriate form - for all participants/activities where necessary. We can distinguish action-oriented knowledge selection and archival knowledge-oriented selection. Action-oriented knowledge selection refers to knowledge absorption from the process of ongoing knowledge creation, that is, absorption of knowledge that has not yet received its final form. These are activities such as: participating in in-house training; seeking out people's know-how, know-what and know-way; awareness of processes and events in the organization, observing behaviors of participants in an organization. On the other hand, archival-oriented knowledge selection implies the acceptance of knowledge from the source where it has been kept, such as selecting an appropriate procedure for forecasting, extracting needed information from a repository, using an organizational memory system, etc.
3. **Knowledge generation** includes two sub-activities: knowledge discovery and knowledge derivation. Knowledge discovery refers to the creation of knowledge based on creativity, imagination and synthesis. Here we have: devising/developing a strategy, developing new products and processes, data mining, creating, generating through collaboration, etc. Also, the creation of new knowledge can be achieved through application of analytical and deductive methods upon the existing resource of knowledge, which has been known as knowledge derivation. Inside this subset of activities we can classify: improving processes through experience in use, improving processes through process analysis, constructing a software routine, etc.
4. **Knowledge assimilation** involves activities that change the company's knowledge level based on internal distribution and storage of knowledge gathered from external and

internal sources, as well as knowledge created by the company. These activities may have a one-way flow (publishing), or they can be multidirectional/ have return flow (interaction). In the first case, we make distinction between so-called formal internal publishing (e.g., publishing a policy manual) and informal internal publishing (e.g., posting an idea on an intranet), and in the second case, we distinguish a formal internal interaction (e.g., bringing experts and people with similar interests together) and informal internal interaction (e.g., mentoring).

5. **Knowledge emission** is the last stage in the knowledge management process that incorporates a resource of knowledge into the company's outputs which will be placed in the business environment. It's a case of extrovert oriented activities and it stands opposite to knowledge assimilation activities where knowledge is retained within the company. Knowledge emission can be formal or informal, as well as one way emission or multicasting. In this sense, we make distinction between formal external publishing (e.g., developing an advertisement), informal external publishing (e.g., using ad hoc press releases), formal external interaction (e.g., providing technical support) and informal external interaction (e.g., using unscripted interviews).

Secondary knowledge chain model activities

Interaction between certain categories of primary activities as well as sub-category interaction inside one category is under the influence of the external environmental factors, company controlled resources and the means of execution of secondary knowledge chain model activities. The contribution of secondary activities in achieving effectiveness and efficiency of primary activities is reflected in enabling, facilitating, supporting, coordinating and motivating the performance of primary activities.

Secondary knowledge chain model activities include the following categories (with associated sub-activities) (Holsapple and Jones, 2005):

1. **Knowledge measurement** incorporates the set of activities used for evaluating the process of knowledge management. All activities (i.e., both primary and secondary), used resources, processors and generated results are assessed, as well as the overall knowledge management contribution. Knowledge measurement is carried out in two phases. The first phase determines the subject of the measurement (what is supposed to be measured) and dimensions of measurement (whether we measure quality or quantity or both). The results are then used for the development of qualitative/quantitative measure. This includes activities such as benchmarking, establishing success metrics early, identifying most important key performance indicators (KPI), using different measures for different stakeholders, etc. Then comes the second stage - applying measures which encompass activities such as: measuring knowledge resources, measuring KM abilities/skills, measuring KM activities, tracking information stakeholders, valuing knowledge, managing/monitoring KM, measuring effects of KM.
2. **Knowledge control** is the group of activities used to ensure that knowledge resource and knowledge processors are available in the required quantity and quality, with respect to requirements related to safety. Some of these activities are more focused on resources, while others are concerned with managerial aspects of control. Accordingly, there are two sub-groups of activities: KM resource control and governance. KM resource control activities include: controlling financial resources available for KM, controlling KM processors, quality controlling, auditing knowledge, while governance sub-group activities include: protecting/providing access controls, using a standard risk management, managing/monitoring KM.

3. **Knowledge coordination** is a harmonized act of creation of a satisfactory outcome while, at the same time, it strives to avoid an unsatisfactory outcome. It is related to the alignment of the interdependent links between the individual elements of the knowledge management process. The focus of knowledge coordination activities is placed on the relations between knowledge resources and other resources (financial, human and material), relations between specific knowledge activities as well as upon relations between knowledge resources and knowledge management activities. The goal is to award the appropriate skills to the various activities of knowledge chain model, to properly schedule the aforementioned activities, and to properly integrate the knowledge management process and other organizational processes. Activities such as: establishing communication patterns, building infrastructure, structuring knowledge work, allocating knowledge workers are aimed at establishing a structure on the basis of which knowledge management will be implemented and, therefore, they are called structuring efforts. The second group of activities are marked as securing efforts and it includes: explaining KM to employees, establishing incentives and motivating employees, securing sponsorship.
4. **Knowledge leadership** encompasses a set of activities that aim to establish the conditions for enabling, motivating and ensuring the implementation of knowledge management. The set can be divided into activities that are carried out before the implementation of knowledge management, and activities that carry out implementations. For example, the first group of activities (planning) includes: analyzing the business case, aligning KM with business strategies, KM establishing guidelines, and the second one (executing) includes: creating a KM culture, delegating activities, sharing the leader's knowledge.

The impact of knowledge resources and the knowledge management process upon innovation and organizational performance of the company

The knowledge chain model focuses on knowledge resources and activities aimed at the creation and manipulation of those resources. The model enables the identification, design and implementation of individual activities and sub-activities of the knowledge management processes, as well as the analysis of their performance, their relationship and connection with other processes and the company's activities, resources engaged, initiated costs and the value they create. In this way it is possible to diagnose the areas in which a knowledge resource can be adequately and fully utilized in order to improve performance, enhance competitive position, or at least, avoid the competitive gap.

Figure 1 indicates that the final result of knowledge management represents an increase in the level of organizational knowledge and its distribution in the company's environment with the distinct knowledge component. The acquisition of knowledge itself (organizational learning) is a necessary but not a sufficient output of the knowledge management process. While knowledge can be created without obvious intention to be used, projections/innovations ensure benefit for the company through the commercialization of knowledge incorporated in the company's output. Accordingly, the knowledge management process and its formalization in terms of the knowledge chain model has an obvious contribution to the introduction, adoption and intensification of innovative behavior of the companies.

The output of the knowledge management process can be manifested in the form of product knowledge, customer knowledge, and managerial knowledge (Tanriverdi and Venkatraman 2005, in Holsapple and Wu, 2008). Product knowledge allows the company to use existing product research and product development results as well as operational knowledge in the field of new product development, shorten cycle times and reduce overall costs. Awareness regarding the customer needs, its preferences and purchasing behavior improves the quality of provided services

and contributes to sale increase because satisfied customers will buy again. Finally, the knowledge management practices, policies and processes can contribute to productivity increase (by reducing waste and avoiding the repetition of mistakes and preventing duplication of operations) and improve agility through faster response to the constant changes in the environment.

With regard to all the aforementioned, we can conclude that the implications of knowledge management initiatives exert a positive effect on organizational performance, i.e., the results (effects) of its operations. The knowledge chain model greatly facilitates the identification of this relation, whether we consider the performance in terms of competitive performance or in terms of financial performance. Achieving superior competitive performance could be reached by placing the focus of the knowledge management process on: improving productivity, improving agility, encouraging innovation and improving reputation. On the other hand, the design of adequate knowledge chain model activity, in order to achieve higher levels of organizational learning and innovation, improves financial performance expressed in the form of profit ratios (as return/assets, return/sales, or operating income/employee) and cost ratios such as operating expense/sales or cost of goods sold/sales. The goal of the company is to maximize profits ratio and minimizes the cost ratio.

Conclusion

Uncompromising demands of contemporary business conditions force companies to focus on knowledge resource and its proper management simply because the ability to learn and innovate holds a key to survival and progress. Regardless of this fact, it is evident that there are some companies that lack a grasp of logic and do not comprehend the significance of knowledge management. Also, there are some companies that do not go beyond the intuitive understanding of knowledge management's essential elements. This paper presents a conceptual framework which, in a structured and categorized way, illustrates and analyzes the process of manipulation of knowledge resources in order to outline the importance of its implementation and points out a proper way to design its key elements (activities, processes, resources).

The knowledge chain model, the same as Porter's value chain, promotes an analysis based on activities. Activities, as separable sequences of processes, consume time and resources while creating value and, therefore, influence the relative cost position and/or differentiation of the company. The knowledge chain model allows us to determine which specific activities of the knowledge management process should be considered in order to improve performance and ensure favourable competitive position, since the knowledge and its effective management are the main factors which determine the level of organizational performance and the degree of competitive advantage.